

**Structural and microwave characterization of $\text{Li}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{MoO}_4$ in 12-18 GHz
region prepared by solid state reaction method**

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Abstract:

In the present work, low temperature firing $\text{Li}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{MoO}_4$, has been prepared via solid state reaction method and its microwave absorption properties in the 12-18 GHz region have been studied. The Thermogravimetric analysis showed $\text{Li}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{MoO}_4$ was thermally stable after 500°C. The structural and microstructural characterizations of the prepared sample were examined through different techniques using XRD, SEM and FTIR spectroscopy. Furthermore, the microwave properties such as reflection loss, shielding effectiveness of the sample were explored in detail. The as synthesized $\text{Li}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{MoO}_4$ shows the high reflection loss (RL) value of -35.96 dB (>99.9% power absorption) at 14.2 GHz and shielding effectiveness (SE) of -21.83 dB at 13.4 GHz. The RL and SE values observed here are relatively high and could meet the requirement for its use in practical applications.

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